

Innovating to Improve – An Experience in a Computer Engineering Programme

M. Teresa T. Monteiro¹, Gabriel Hornink², Flávia Vieira³

¹ ALGORITMI Centre, Department of Production and Systems, School of Engineering, University of Minho, Guimarães, Portugal

² Educational Media Laboratory, Department of Biochemistry, Institute of Biomedical Sciences, Federal University of Alfenas, Brazil

³ Centro de Investigação em Educação (CIEd), Institute of Education, University of Minho, Braga, Portugal

Email: tm@dps.uminho.pt, gabriel.hornink@unifal-mg.edu.br, flaviav@ie.uminho.pt

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5095687>

Abstract

This paper presents a pedagogical experience carried out in a course unit of a master's programme in Computer Engineering at the University of Minho. The course unit, Numerical Methods and Nonlinear Optimization, is placed in the first semester of the third year and the experience took place with 184 students in the academic year 2020-2021. Until then, it had been taught in a traditional way, with theoretical lectures and practical classes for solving exercises. There were several reasons to innovate, namely the need to move to online teaching due to COVID-19, which was an opportunity to introduce new methodologies and technologies, but also the need to foster students' engagement and performance. A b-learning approach was implemented through a combination of strategies and resources, aiming to enhance motivation, interaction and participation in learning. Assessment was more diversified and distributed over time to foster ongoing study and progress. It included mini-tests and two MatLab projects carried out in teams with the main challenge of finding a real-world phenomenon for the application of a course concept, which implied connecting conceptual learning with reality and creating bridges with other areas of knowledge. The experience was evaluated on the basis of students' assessment results and their perceptions collected in a survey. The new approach resulted in high levels of student engagement and satisfaction, promoting cooperation and the personal construction of knowledge, which are essential competences for lifelong learning. Nevertheless, the development of MatLab projects requires further improvements, not only as regards support to students but also the evaluation of their impact on learning.

Keywords: Innovation; B-learning; Engagement; Mathematics Education.

1 Introduction

The situation of lockdown due to the pandemic COVID-19 in the second semester of 2019/2020 forced universities to move to online teaching. At the University of Minho, teachers and students made significant efforts to adapt to this new reality and the Centre IDEA-UMinho (Centre for the Innovation and Development of Teaching and Learning - <https://idea.uminho.pt/pt>) had a significant role in supporting faculty through teacher training actions (see Hornink, Costa & Vieira, 2020).

In the first semester of 2020/2021, a hybrid approach to teaching was adopted across the institution: online teaching was particularly recommended for theoretical classes, and face-to-face teaching was considered to be important for practical and lab classes. The first author attended a training course where participants were challenged to plan a b-learning approach to be implemented in a course unit (CU), and she decided to innovate the CU Numerical Methods and Nonlinear Optimization (NMNO), which is part of a master's programme in Computer Engineering. The main goal of innovation was to foster students' engagement and performance by using active methodologies mediated by digital technologies and by enhancing ongoing study and progress in assessment.

The following sections focus on the context of the experience and the changes implemented in theoretical lectures and assessment procedures (section 2), the findings of the experience, based on the analysis of students' assessment results and their perceptions of the approach (section 3), and the conclusions and current developments of the experience (section 4).

2 The pedagogical experience

2.1 The context

NMNO is placed in the first semester of the third year of a master's programme in Computer Engineering that integrates the first and second cycle of studies, with a duration of 5 academic years, 10 academic semesters, 40 weeks of full-time study per year, and a total of 300 ECTS. During the programme, students acquire theoretical knowledge and practical experience regarding the analysis of software systems and the specification of those systems' requirements, the techniques for building prototypes and all the phases of their installation, the management of computer projects, the processes of testing, installation and maintenance of computer applications, and the systems or networks that support them.

The experience took place with 184 students in the first semester of the academic year 2020-2021. The CU NMNO has 5 ECTS (140 working hours) and consists of two distinct modules: Numerical Methods and Nonlinear Optimization. The learning outcomes of the UC are the following: applying computer tools to model physical problems; developing and applying numerical skills to analyse systems; comparing different solutions for numerical problems; selecting, using and comparing different optimization algorithms; developing critical evaluation of results; and using computational tools. It is taught 4h a week: 2h of theoretical classes (TCs) and 2h of practical classes (PCs).

Before the pandemics, TCs were taught face-to-face in a large auditorium, with the support of slides that were made available to the students at the institutional platform (Blackboard), which can be used as a repository of lesson contents and materials. Given the high number of students in class, interaction was kept to a minimum. There were six PCs in computational laboratories with about 30 students per group. When b-learning was implemented, TCs were taught online two days a week (1h+1h) in the BlackBoard Collaborate Ultra platform, and three face-to-face PCs (2h) were carried out with about 60 students. The CU involved four teachers, but the innovation process was implemented by the first author in TCs and in assessment; PCs were kept in the same format, although one of them was taught face-to-face and online simultaneously.

Students from this programme usually like digital tools and have digital competences, therefore the use of digital technology was expected to be appropriate. However, since NMNO is not a specialized CU in the programme, in the teacher's perception, the students tend to underestimate its value and application, and it was important to change this attitude by enhancing their engagement in learning. Moreover, over the years, they felt that a lot of content was covered in tests, leading some to drop out. Changes in assessment were also needed, namely by diversifying assessment tasks and distributing them over time to foster ongoing study and progress.

2.2 Changing theoretical classes

Online TCs involved synchronous and asynchronous activities. Two virtual murals were created in Padlet (<https://padlet.com>) to support learning, one with general information about the CU and the other, updated weekly, providing information on all the activities related to the CU.

Synchronous activities consisted of theoretical lessons (twice a week) via Blackboard Collaborate Ultra, which were recorded to allow students to revise them or attend them in case they missed them. Before each lesson, during 10 minutes, music was played to create a relaxing atmosphere. Some lessons started with storytelling, for example about some interesting details of a mathematician's biography or real-world applications related to the CU concepts. Another strategy for introducing content was the use of appealing short videos on practical applications of the concepts taught and the resolution of exercises. Once a week, in order to verify whether the concepts were understood by the students, the Audience Response Systems (ARS) methodology was used through Voxvote (<https://www.voxvote.com>). A few multiple choice questions were given to the students, who were grouped in breakout rooms to analyse and decide on the correct answers, using their mobiles to respond. Then, the students and the teacher got together in the main room, discussing the student's choices and clarifying any doubts.

Asynchronous activities were mostly related to assessment, namely the development of two MatLab projects described in more detail in section 2.3. They entailed a problem-based learning approach where students had

to find a real-world phenomenon for the application of a course concept. Projects were developed in teams and supervised in tutorial sessions.

Although TCs still focused on theoretical learning as a basis for PCs, there was an effort to make them more motivating and engaging. Storytelling and videos were aimed at contextualizing contents and connecting them with real-life experience. Voxvote allowed students to interact, review lesson contents, self-assess their learning and get feedback from their peers and the teacher, which was aimed at enhancing conceptual understanding and self-regulation skills (Evans, 2013). Project development was intended to connect conceptual learning with reality and enhance self-direction, cooperation, problem-solving and interdisciplinary learning, which are important elements of active learning (Graaff & Kolmos, 2003; Prince, 2004).

2.3 Changing assessment practices

Before the experience, assessment took place in the middle and at the end of the semester. Each moment included a face-to-face written test and a test on the computer using MatLab. In order to foster ongoing study and progress, assessment practices were more diversified and distributed over time. They still included two written tests done face-to-face (one per module, 50% of total assessment), but two new tasks were added: four online multiple choice mini-tests (two per module, 30% of total assessment) and two MatLab group projects (one per module, 20% of total assessment).

Mini-tests were carried out monthly with an average duration of 12 minutes. They focused on course topics through multiple choice questions (3 to 5 per test), randomly generated from extensive banks with more than 700 questions. The tests were carried out online during TCs and without the possibility of going backwards. The intention was to assess the apprehension of key-concepts and foster the student's commitment to ongoing study and timely remediation of difficulties found. Feedback was provided later by focusing on students' main difficulties.

Two MatLab projects were carried out outside the classroom in teams of four elements, chosen by the students, with the main challenge of finding a real-world phenomenon for the application of a course concept. The content of the first project focused on the Numerical Methods module and the second on Nonlinear Optimization. If the sum of the students' mechanographic numbers were even (21 teams) the course concept was Nonlinear Equations (fsolve MatLab routine), otherwise (21 teams) it was Least Squares Technique (polyfit and lsqcurvefit MatLab routines). Project development entailed connecting conceptual learning with reality and creating bridges with other scientific areas. Interdisciplinary learning is illustrated in Table 1, which summarises the scientific areas and the specific topics covered in the first project.

Table 1. Project 1 (Numerical methods)

Main Scientific area	Number of projects	Topics
Astronomy	2	orbit intersection, collisions
Biology	3	dating fossils, Escherichia coli bacteria, oxygen level in sewer
Chemistry	3	air compression factor, tank reactors in series, spherical tank with rod
Economics	4	Gold value, PIB, Bitcoin, dollar euro exchange
Electronics	2	GPS receiver, sound
Geography	3	Temperature in regions, global warming
Health	3	Covid-19
Industrial Engineering	2	profit from selling computers
Informatics	1	CPU price
Physics	9	throwing objects, impacts, pendulum, military confrontation, floating ball, missile trajectory, friction
Sociology	7	unemployment rate, birth rate per year, world population growth, condemnations for sexual abuse
Sports, others	3	American soccer, income movie

This task also aimed at developing and evaluating the MatLab practice. During its resolution, the students had several online tutorial meetings with teachers. Assessment criteria were: originality, complexity, the adequacy of computational experiments using MatLab and the quality of the final report (limited to 3 pages).

3 Findings

To evaluate the experience, two methods were used: the analysis of students' assessment results and an online survey administered in the middle of the semester to get their feedback on the approach used.

3.1 Assessment results

Out of the 184 students enrolled in the CU, 164 were assessed and only 6 failed to achieve a positive grade, which means that 96.34% passed, with grades ranging from 10 to 20 (on a 0-20 assessment scale). Out of these, only 6 had to go through a final written exam because they did not get a positive grade in continuous assessment (tests, mini-tests and projects). These results show that the new assessment methodology appears to have worked for most students. Figure 1 shows the distribution of grades.

Figure 1. Students' final grades.

Mini-tests were aimed at promoting ongoing study, which appears to have been the case for most students if we look at the results in Tables 2-5. The absence rate was low, indicating their commitment to ongoing assessment, although it is still problematic that 5.4% to 12.37% missed one or more tests.

Table 2. Mini-test 1 (3 questions).

Points	15	10	5	0	absence
Students (%)	65.4	26	3	0	5.4

Table 3. Mini-test 2 (5 questions).

Points	15	12	9	6	3	0	absence
Students (%)	22.46	30.48	26.20	11.23	2.14	1.07	6.42

Table 4. Mini-test 3 (5 questions).

Points	15	12	9	6	3	0	absence
Students (%)	35.83	32.62	13.9	3.74	3.21	1.07	9.09

Table 5. Mini-test 4 (3 questions).

Points	15	10	5	0	absence
Students (%)	46.24	27.96	9.68	3.76	12.37

Projects are expected to engage students in creative and self-directed forms of learning, but that does not necessarily mean that students' grades in projects are better than their grades in written tests. A comparison was done between the grades obtained in projects and in the two written tests by the 158 students who were assessed. Project grades were better than test grades for 57 students (36.1%), and test grades were better than project grades for 101 students (63.9%).

Project grades have a 0 - 40 points range. Test grades have a 0 - 100 points range. For analysis purposes, project and test grades have been converted into a common measurement scale: 0 to 200 points. For example, a student with a 40 points project and a 100 points test (maximum grades), in this common scale, has both a 200 points project and a 200 points test. Let P_i be the grades of projects and T_i the grades of tests, with $1 \leq i \leq 158$. Let $|P_i - T_i|$ be the absolute difference between the project grade of a student and the test grade of the same student. After calculating the differences for all students, and the average of these values, the results that came up were the following.

The average difference between project grades and test grades was 38.69, the maximum gap between the project grade of a student and the grade of tests of the same student was 104.6.

These results can perhaps be explained by the complexity and unfamiliarity of project work. Despite tutorial sessions, a wide range of grades was obtained in projects, showing students' diversity regarding their ability to apply concepts to real-life phenomena and undertake self-directed learning effectively. Tests, on the other hand, focused mainly on conceptual understanding, and the use of regular mini-tests and question-answer quizzes in TCs may have prepared students to cope with them more confidently.

Project and test grades were also compared with final grades (Table 6). About 2/3 of the students (107 students) had better final grades than project grades. About 1/2 of the students (79 students) had better final grades than test grades.

Table 6. Comparison between project, test and final grades.

	better than Final Grade	worse than Final Grade	= Final Grade
Project Grade	49 (31%)	107 (67.7%)	2 (1.3%)
Test/Exam Grade	74 (46.8%)	79 (50%)	5 (3.2%)

It was concluded that when tests are taken into account, grades go up in relation to project grades. On the other hand, there is a greater balance between test grades and final grades. The following patterns were further detected:

As the grades of tests increase, the final grades also increase through an exact linear rule;

When looking for correlations between project grades and final grades, both grades tend to go up in response to one another, but this relationship is not very strong because there is a significant number of cases where this is not true.

These results are explained below in greater detail.

Let P_i be the grades of projects, T_i the grades of tests and F_i the final grades, with $1 \leq i \leq 158$. The Pearson correlation coefficient between P_i and F_i , with $1 \leq i \leq 158$, is 0.62. This means that there is a moderate positive linear relationship between the grades of projects and the final grades. While both grades tend to go up in relation to one another, the relationship is not very strong. This may be partially explained by a high variation of project grades as mentioned above. On the other hand, the correlation coefficient between tests and final

grades is 1. This means that there's a perfect linear correlation between the grades of tests and the final grades: as the grades of tests increase, the final grades also increase through an exact linear rule. This seems to suggest that tests played a more prominent role in the final grades.

We also looked at other indicators such as: the gaps between the grades of tests and final grades, the gaps between project grades and final grades, and the gaps between test and project grades.

Let:

$|T_i - F_i|$ be the absolute difference between the grade of the tests of students and the final grade of the same student;

$|P_i - F_i|$ be the absolute difference between the project grade of students and the final grade of the same student;

TminusF be the average of all $|T_i - F_i|$, where $1 \leq i \leq 158$;

PminusF be the average of all $|P_i - F_i|$, where $1 \leq i \leq 158$.

Since TminusF is 10.31 and PminusF is 33.53, the average gap between final grades and project grades is almost the triple of the average gap between final grades and the grades of tests.

Let:

GP be the maximum gap between the project grade of a student and the final grade of the same student, or more exactly the maximum of all $|P_i - F_i|$, where

$1 \leq i \leq 158$;

GT be the maximum gap between the grade of the tests of a student and the final grade of the same student, or more exactly the maximum of all $|T_i - F_i|$, where

$1 \leq i \leq 158$.

Since GP is 126.6 and GT is 41, the first gap is almost the triple of the second gap. There is no significant correlation between the gaps $|P_i - F_i|$ and final grades, where $1 \leq i \leq 158$. There is also no significant correlation between the gaps $|T_i - F_i|$ and final grades, where $1 \leq i \leq 158$.

The only correlation worth mentioning is the one between the gaps $|P_i - F_i|$ and final grades when project grades are better than final grades. In this case, the correlation coefficient between the gaps $|P_i - F_i|$ and final grades is -0.6. This means that as the project grades and the final grades become further apart, final grades decrease, and as the project grades and the final grades become closer to each other, the final grades increase, although this relationship is moderate.

The analysis of students' assessment results seems to suggest that project development requires further improvements to ensure better quality outcomes for more students, which demands a closer look at students' difficulties and the enactment of better support strategies.

3.2 Students' perceptions

In the middle of the semester, in order to monitor the impact of innovation, a short Google forms survey with 5 questions was implemented (106 students answered the survey). Three closed questions focused on: the percentage synchronous classes attended by students (<25/25-50/50-75/>75); the form of attendance (synchronous/asynchronous); and the use of recorded lessons (always/sometimes/never). Two open questions were intended to gather students' opinions about what they appreciated and would like to change in the TCs.

About 85% of the students attended more than 75% of TCs, 87% of them synchronously, which is a relatively high degree of attendance given the fact that students often miss theoretical lessons. Regarding the recorded lessons, 41% always used them and 54% used them sometimes as their learning method, which appears to suggest that lesson recording may support student learning, provided that it does not discourage them to attend lessons, where they can interact directly with peers and the teacher.

Regarding the aspects appreciated by the students (Table 7), their replies were grouped according to their main focus: 'planning' (e.g., lesson organization, examples, solved exercises), 'technologies' (e.g., VoxVote and Padlet), 'methodologies' (teaching and assessment practices) and 'teacher' (the teacher's characteristics and way of teaching). A total of 258 references to these aspects were identified, showing that the approach was valued. Some students say that mini-tests allowed them to be more connected to the CU, preparing them step-by-step to the face-to-face written tests. Voxvote activities were also perceived as important to facilitate conceptual understanding and the clarification of doubts.

Table 7. Aspects appreciated by students.

Strategy	No. of references
Planning	121
Technologies	59
Methodologies	48
Teacher	30

As regards what students would like to change, two suggestions were presented: 20 students mentioned they would like to have more time to answer the questions of Voxvote, and 7 would like to solve more exercises in class. These aspects were taken into account by the teacher for the rest of the semester.

The students' perceptions in the institutional feedback survey they fill in at the end of each semester were also positive: in the pedagogical dimension, the CU was perceived to have worked in an appropriate way, with an average value of 4.7 in 5-point scale, which was higher than the average value for all the CUs at the Engineering School (3.8) and at the University of Minho (4.0). Furthermore, some students emphasized the positive and joyful environment of the lessons and a focus on learning based on interpersonal understanding and gratitude for learning, never neglecting rigor and professionalism.

4 Conclusions and current developments

The new approach fostered students' engagement and satisfaction, although assessment results were quite varied. Mini-tests and classroom quizzes through VoxVote were important to enhance ongoing study and conceptual learning, and to prepare students for written tests. However, projects appeared to demand a lot from students and there was a wide variation in their quality. Project development enacted some of the conditions for creating 'situated learning environments' in higher education as pointed out by Herrington (2006): an authentic context that reflects the way knowledge will be used in real life; authentic activities which have real-world relevance, and which present a single complex task to be completed over a sustained period of time; collaborative construction of knowledge; coaching and scaffolding by peers and teachers; and authentic assessment by integrating learning and assessment into the same task. Projects also entailed interdisciplinary learning, enabling students to deal with topics from diverse scientific areas. Nevertheless, students appear to need more support for developing this type of project, especially because it is not a familiar task and it demands competences they may not possess.

The approach is being currently expanded and consolidated with other students and with institutional support from Centre IDEA-UMinho. The project was proposed to the Centre in late 2020 within a programme that supports innovative pedagogical projects. It was accepted in January 2020 and the second and third authors were allocated by the Centre as tutors. Support to the development of students' projects is one of the aspects under improvement by clarifying quality criteria, discussing them with students, giving them an example of a good project, and turning the first project into a trial activity whereby they can experience and surpass difficulties without being assessed. Other strategies to enhance the quality of projects might include forming heterogeneous groups according to students' prior competences to foster cooperative learning, and integrating problem-based and project-based learning strategies into classes. Another improvement to this experience relates to how it is evaluated. Student perceptions will be collected twice (in the beginning and at

the end of the semester), and more attention will be paid to the qualitative analysis of projects as a source of evidence about students' competences and difficulties, and about the importance of projects for connecting concepts with real-life phenomena and developing interdisciplinary learning.

As teachers innovate, investigate and disseminate their own teaching practice, they engage in the scholarship of teaching and learning - SoTL (Felten, 2013; Shulman, 2004). This form of understanding and developing one's profession requires an ongoing reflective stance towards teaching and learning, along with collaboration among faculty in trying to innovate and make sense of experience. The programme of Centre IDEA-UMinho provides an opportunity for enhancing SoTL with the support of faculty mentors who act as critical friends, which surely helps to improve pedagogy in a collaborative and sustainable way.

Acknowledgments

This work has been supported by FCT – Fundação para a Ciência e Tecnologia within the R&D Units Project Scope: UIDB/00319/2020.

5 References

- Evans, C. (2013). Making sense of assessment feedback in higher education. *Review of Educational Research*, 82(1), 70-120. <https://doi.org/10.3102/0034654312474350>
- Felten, P. (2013). *Principles of good practice in SoTL*. *Teaching & Learning Inquiry*, 1(1), 121-125. <https://journalhosting.ucalgary.ca/index.php/TLI/article/view/57376/43149>
- Graaff, E. D., & Kolmos, A. (2003). Characteristics of problem-based learning. *International Journal of Engineering Education*, 19(5), 657-662. <http://www.ijee.ie/articles/Vol19-5/IJEE1450.pdf>
- Herrington, J. (2006). Authentic e-learning in higher education: Design principles for authentic learning environments and tasks. *World Conference on E-Learning in Corporate, Government, Healthcare, and Higher Education, Chesapeake, Va.* https://www.researchgate.net/publication/30388215_Authentic_e-learning_in_higher_education_Design_principles_for_authentic_learning_environments_and_tasks
- Hornink G. G., Vieira F., & Costa M. J. (2020). O papel do Centro IDEA-UMinho na transição para o ensino on-line durante a pandemia COVID-19: Enfrentar desafios e criar oportunidades. In M. Martins & E. Rodrigues (Eds). *A Universidade do Minho em tempos de pandemia: Tomo II: (Re)Ações* (pp. 174-210). Braga: UMinho Editora. <https://ebooks.uminho.pt/index.php/uminho/catalog/book/26>
- Prince, M. (2004). Does active learning work? A review of the research. *Journal of Engineering Education*, 93(3), 223-231. <https://doi.org/10.1002/j.2168-9830.2004.tb00809.x>
- Shulman, L. (2004). Teaching as community property – Essays on higher education. *Coletânea ed. por P. Hutchings*. San Francisco: Jossey-Bass.